

SELF-PACED LEARNING (CANVAS)

Kasmawati

1801121332

081257762417 (wa)

- Canvas is one of many kind of online course.
- Canvas is free to access.

What is canvas?

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- Canvas allows students to work at their own pace, which helps teachers provide students with a personalized educational experience.

Why I chose canvas?

Developing Self-Paced Learning course

Course

Log in to your account

Choose the course

Read the material

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a Canvas LMS course page. The browser's address bar shows the URL: https://canvas.instructure.com/courses/2488288/pages/introduction-to-the-course?module_item_id=40057164. The page header includes the Canvas logo and the course title "ENGLISH > Pages > Introduction to the course".

On the left side, there is a vertical navigation menu with the following items: Home, Assignments, Discussions, Grades, People, Pages (highlighted), Files, Syllabus, Quizzes, Modules, Conferences, and Collaborations. Below these are icons for Account, Dashboard, Courses, Calendar, Inbox, History, Conferences, and Help.

The main content area is titled "Introduction to the course" and contains the following text:

With this course, you will understand the use of Passive Voice.

At the start of this course you will be introduced to the definition of Passive Voice. You will then learn the rules of using Passive Voice with the patterns.

Next, you will learn about the example sentence of Passive Voice. The course also teaches you how to make a Passive Voice sentence. Finally, you will learn how to make an Passive Voice.

By the end of this online course, you will have a much stronger understanding of Passive Voice that can be used into daily conversation.

So why wait? Try the course now, and bring your English language skills to the next level in just a few short hours.

Buttons for "View All Pages" and "Next" are visible on the page.

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a Canvas LMS page. The browser's address bar shows the URL: https://canvas.instructure.com/courses/248288/pages/outcomes-and-objectives-of-the-course/module_item_at+400. The page title is "ENGLISH > Pages > Outcomes and Objectives of the course".

On the left side, there is a dark navigation sidebar with the following items: Canvas logo, Account, Dashboard, Courses, Calendar, Inbox, History, Conferences, and Help.

The main content area has a breadcrumb trail: "ENGLISH > Pages > Outcomes and Objectives of the course". Below this, there is a "View All Pages" button. The main heading is "Outcomes and Objectives of the course".

Under the heading, there is a section titled "Outcomes:" followed by a bulleted list:

- You are able to understand of Passive Voice.
- You are able to use Passive Voice.
- You can use and remember the form of verb 3.
- You are able to use Passive Voice in daily conversation.

At the bottom of the list, there is a "Previous" button on the left and a "Next" button on the right. The "Next" button is highlighted in black and contains the text "Next Module: PASSIVE VOICE".

The bottom of the browser window shows the Windows taskbar with the time 3:07 PM.

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ENGLISH Quizzes Passive Voice QUIZ

Passive Voice QUIZ

Due Jan 10, 2021 at 11:59pm Points 6 Questions 6
Available Dec 29 at 12am - Jan 11, 2021 at 11:59pm 14 days Time Limit 100 Minutes
Allowed Attempts 2

Instructions

Please answer the questions.

[Take the Quiz](#)

[Previous](#)

Canvas LMS sidebar navigation:
Home
Assignments
Discussions
Grades
People
Pages
Files
Syllabus
Quizzes
Modules
Conferences
Collaborations

Windows taskbar: 11:38 PM

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a Canvas LMS quiz. The browser's address bar shows the URL: <https://canvas.instructure.com/courses/2488788/quizzes/6739511/attempt/questions/10070985>. The page title is "ENGLISH > Quizzes > Passive Voice QUIZ".

Passive Voice QUIZ
Started: Dec 30 at 8:23am

Quiz Instructions
Please answer the questions.

Questions

- ✓ Question 1
- ✓ Question 2
- ✓ Question 3
- ⓪ Question 4
- ⓪ Question 5
- ⓪ Question 6

Time Running: [Hide](#)
Attempt due: Jan 10, 2023 at 11:59pm
1 Hour, 38 Minutes, 54 Seconds

Question 4 1 pts

school will be being.....during the summer.

- close
- closed
- closing

Navigation: [← Previous](#) [Next →](#)

The interface includes a left-hand navigation menu with options: Home, Assignments, Discussions, Grades, People, Pages, Files, Syllabus, Quizzes, Modules, Conferences, Collaborations, Account, Dashboard, Courses, Calendar, Inbox, History, Conferences, and Help. The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the time as 3:02 PM.

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http://forvaler.instructure.com/courses/2488788/quizzes/6733511

Attempt History

	Attempt	Time	Score
LATEST	Attempt 1	2 minutes	6 out of 6

Score for this attempt: 6 out of 6
Submitted Dec 30 at 8:25am
This attempt took 2 minutes.

Question 1 1 / 1 pts

Brigo is played in Britain:

- active
- passive
- negative
- positive

Correct!

-
- <https://canvas.instructure.com/register>
 - Class code : 63H9F7

**YOU CAN TRY IT!! THANK U,
NEXT.**
